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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO DETERMINE THE
INTENSITY AND FREQUENCY OF SHOULDER PAIN
AMONG STROKE SURVIVORS**¹Dr. Andleeb Tariq, ²Dr. Rafia Anser, ³Dr. Kiran Latif¹THQ Pindigheb²Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi³Lahore General Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Objective: The objective of this research study was to determine the intensity and occurrence of shoulder pain among patients of stroke. The research was also aimed to determine the primary aetiology of stroke and involved side of pain along with the relationship between both.

Patients and Methods: This cross-sectional research was carried out in the course of February to August 2019 at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore on a total of one hundred patients who fulfilled WHO sample selection criteria. Both males and females were included in the research sample fulfilling the WHO definition of stroke. All the patients were reported within the timeframe of one year of pain. We did not include any patients who were reported for rheumatic disease, cognitive dysfunction and chronic pain patients. The pain that required analgesia for more than two continuous days was graded as shoulder pain which was scaled on the visual analogue scale.

Results: In the total population of one hundred patients the calculated mean age was (63 ± 18) years. Females dominated males in the sample population. Total 24% of patients were males while the remaining 76% were females. Primary aetiology of ischemic stroke was present in 50 patients (62.5%) and absent in 30 patients (37.5%). Primary aetiology of hemorrhagic stroke was present in 8 patients (40%) and absent in 12 patients (60%). Left side pain was present among 32 patients (72.7%) and absent among 12 patients (27.3%); whereas, right-hand side pain was present among 26 patients (46.4%) and absent among 30 patients (53.6%). Majority of the patients (83.3%) reported moderate to severe pain. Left side pain was more prevalent with a proportion of (72.7%) among (62.5%) ischemic stroke patients. These associations were also statistically significant (respective P-values 0.061 and 0.197).

Conclusion: Majority of the patients experiencing stroke developed shoulder pain in the first year and mostly reported moderate to severe pain. There was no significant relation between shoulder pain with side of involvement and primary aetiology of stroke.

Keywords: Stroke, Shoulder Pain, Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), Primary Etiology, Ischemic and Hemorrhagic.

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INTRODUCTION:

Stroke patients commonly report hemiplegic shoulder pain which hinders recovery and also restricts movement. The delayed recovery and movement complications also attribute in the pain scores as observed through VAS. Effective use of rehabilitation approaches primarily aims to reduce the onset of pain. Stroke survivors prolonged hospitalization and delayed rehabilitation most importantly relate to the onset of pain [1]. Stroke patients may suffer from shoulder pain due to rotator cuff tear / impingement, shoulder subluxation, bicipital tendonitis, adhesive capsulitis, or other related reasons [2 – 6]. Pain aetiology after the stroke may be attributed in the initial days improper transfer techniques, bad positioning and trauma [5]. Global shoulder pain prevalence is in the range of 11% to 40% [7]. It also attributes in increased treatment cost, delayed rehabilitation and burden on hospital due to stroke patients [7]. At present very less is known about the intensity, pattern and prevalence of pain intensity among stroke survivors. Therefore, we carried out this research with an objective to determine the intensity and occurrence of shoulder pain among patients of stroke. The research was also aimed to determine the primary aetiology of stroke and involved side of pain along with the relationship between both.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional research was carried out in the course of February to August 2019 at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore on a total of one hundred patients who fulfilled WHO sample selection criteria. Both males and females were included in the research sample fulfilling the WHO definition of stroke. All the patients were reported within the timeframe of one year of pain. We did not include any patients who were reported for rheumatic disease, cognitive dysfunction and chronic pain patients. The pain that required analgesia for more

than two continuous days was graded as shoulder pain which was scaled on the visual analogue scale [9]. Sample selection was made through non-probability consecutive sample selection approach. These patients were enrolled from OPDs of stroke rehabilitation department and wards. The pain was measured on VAS from 0 to 100 mm visual scale as no pain to worst pain. We followed the patients for a period of four months to document shoulder pain increase. SPSS software was used for the statistical analysis. Age was calculated in mean and SD. We presented gender distribution, aetiology of stroke, side of pain and intensity of pain in percentage and frequencies. The association between the side of pain and aetiology of stroke was compared through the Chi-Square test. Significant P-Value was under 0.05.

RESULTS:

In the total population of one hundred patients the calculated mean age was (63 ± 18) years. Females dominated males in the sample population. Total 24% of patients were males while the remaining 76% were females. Primary aetiology of ischemic stroke was present in 50 patients (62.5%) and absent in 30 patients (37.5%). Primary aetiology of hemorrhagic stroke was present in 8 patients (40%) and absent in 12 patients (60%). Left side pain was present among 32 patients (72.7%) and absent among 12 patients (27.3%); whereas, right-hand side pain was present among 26 patients (46.4%) and absent among 30 patients (53.6%). Majority of the patients (83.3%) reported moderate to severe pain. Left side pain was more prevalent with a proportion of (72.7%) among (62.5%) ischemic stroke patients. Pain intensity was reported 42% no pain, 10% not commented, 8% mild pain and 40% moderate to severe pain. These associations were also statistically significant (respective P-values 0.061 and 0.197). Detailed outcomes have also been provided in the tabular and graphical presentation.

Table – I: Characteristics of Pain and Primary Etiology of Stroke

Characteristics		Present		Absent		P-Value
		Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	
Primary etiology of stroke	Ischemic	50	62.5	30	37.5	0.197
	Hemorrhagic	8	40	12	60	
Side of Pain	Left	32	72.7	12	27.3	0.061
	Right	26	46.4	30	53.6	

Table – II: Intensity of Pain

Pain Intensity	Percentage
No Pain	42
Not commented	10
Mild Pain	8
Moderate to Severe	40

DISCUSSION:

Shoulder pain has been considerably debated for its intensity and management but the pain is still prevalent and relevant among stroke patients – it is an accepted inevitable condition which is experienced by stroke survivors [11]. Joint activity is limited because of the onset of shoulder pain which also discourages upper extremity usage and also prevents routine motor activity. Assisting technology is mandatory to recover motor activity. Futuristic and present motor management systems including constraint-induced motor, functional electrical stimulation, virtual reality and robotics

largely depend on the shoulder area movement including shoulder joint which is useless in case the pain is not effectively managed [12 – 16].

International pain scores reported among stroke survivors are different from each other. Out of 46 patients, 17 patients (37%) suffered shoulder pain among which seven were already experiencing the pain before the stroke [17]. Another series reported slightly reduced shoulder pain prevalence of 22% at 4th month follow-up and 24% on 16th month follow-up – it corresponds to another research which reported shoulder pain prevalence of 23% [18].

According to Wanklyn, 20% of patients shown shoulder pain prevalence just after the stroke [19]. Two other similar series conducted their trials on 311 and 152 stroke survivors and reported conflicting pain prevalence rates of respectively 9% and 40% [20, 21]. In this research shoulder, joint pain prevalence was 58% among stroke survivors. This may be because of the inclusion criteria of two days of analgesia continuation among patients. Other research studies remained strict in the patients' selection criteria and enrolled those patients who reported shoulder pain for a minimum of two weeks [9]. Majority of the patients (83.3%) reported moderate to severe pain. On the basis of pain intensity, we can say that mild pain was reported lesser than moderate to severe pain. Another series also reported moderate pain among 79% of stroke survivors along with severe pain among 32% after four months follow-up which gradually reduced to 21% after sixteen months [22].

Ischemic stroke patients commonly reported pain (62.5%); whereas, hemorrhagic stroke patients reported the same as 40%. The dominance of pain is not significant statistically (P-Value = 0.061). Lindgren et al reported slightly increased ischemic stroke onset over hemorrhagic stroke (22.3% versus 17.6%). This time again the statistical difference was not significant (P-Value 0.197). No single pathology is responsible for shoulder pain among stroke survivors. It is difficult to relate it with one pathology. However, four major inciting factors are feeling of pain in shoulder hand, altered sensitivity, muscles and joints [18]. Different pain combinations may be observed in the regular clinical practice which makes the diagnosis process even difficult. Pathology determination needs detailed clinical assessment and imaging which will ultimately assist in effective therapeutic management [23].

Several research studies have focused on shoulder pain prevention strategies. One research put emphasis on the recommendation of a variety of motion exercises to manage shoulder pain [24]. Evidence also shows the effectiveness of supportive devices to prevent pain and shoulder subluxation [25]. Motor recovery and shoulder pain management are also possible through electrical stimulation but reliable outcomes demand more focused studies for reliable outcomes [26]. The population of our country; whereas, our selected population was very small. We also did not include shoulder pain primary aetiology which would have given better results about shoulder pain trends. Although it is a unique effort to explore facts about shoulder pain among stroke survivors but definite pathophysiology of shoulder pain demand more definite research studies by using a combination of both electrophysiological data and imaging on a large-scale population.

CONCLUSION:

Majority of the patients experiencing stroke developed shoulder pain in the first year and mostly reported moderate to severe pain. There was no significant relation between shoulder pain with side of involvement and primary aetiology of stroke.

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